

THE EFFECT OF WORKPLACE BULLYING ON COUNTERPRODUCTIVE WORK BEHAVIOR: AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE OF BANKING EMPLOYEES OF MARDAN

İŞYERİ ZORBALIĞININ ÜRETKENLİK KARŞITI İŞ DAVRANIŞI ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ: MARDAN'DA BANKACILIK ÇALIŞANLARI ÜZERİNDE AMPİRİK BİR ÇALIŞMA

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays workplace bullying is a serious and crucial problem in a corporate environment. The rise of the deviant attitudes of the colleagues and managers toward its employees in the company influences the development of deviant behavior of employees as CWB (counterproductive work behavior) which not only disturbs the productivity and performance of the company but also affects the psychological and physiological health of the employees. Additionally, it also increases the turnover rate of employees in the company. Due to this reason, descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression analyses were used to find out the association between workplace bullying (WB) and counterproductive work behavior (CWB). The data for this research was collected from 125 employees of banks of Mardan, KPK. The result exhibited a positive association between WB (workplace bullying) and CWB (counterproductive work behavior).

Keywords: Workplace Bullying, Counterproductive Work Behavior, Banking Employees.

ÖZET

Günümüzde işyerinde zorbalık, kurumsal bir ortamda ciddi ve çok önemli bir sorundur. Şirkette çalışma arkadaşlarının ve yöneticilerin çalışanlarına yönelik sapkın tutumlarının artması, çalışanların sapkın davranışlarının CWB (üretkenlik karşıtı iş davranışı) olarak gelişimini etkiler. Ki o sadece şirketin verimliliğini ve performansını bozmakla kalmayıp aynı zamanda çalışanların psikolojik ve fizyolojik sağlığını da etkiler. Ayrıca, şirketteki çalışanların devir oranını da artırır. Bu nedenle, işyerinde zorbalık (WB) ile verimsiz iş davranışı (CWB) arasındaki ilişkiyi bulmak için tanımlayıcı istatistikler ve çoklu doğrusal regresyon analizleri kullanılmıştır. Bu araştırma için veriler KPK Mardan bankalarının 125 çalışanından toplanmıştır. Sonuç, WB (işyeri zorbalığı) ve CWB (üretken olmayan iş davranışı) arasında pozitif bir ilişki olduğunu gösterdi.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Üretkenlik Karşıtı İş Davranışı, İşyeri Zorbalığı, Bankacılık Çalışanları.

1. Introduction

Nowadays workplace bullying is a very severe and critical issue in companies that not only affects the organization, but also the health and productivity of the employees in the company. According to Einarsen, (1999) and Mikkelsen (2000), workplace bullying is a situation where an individual is frequently and repeatedly subjected to destructive acts such as frequent abuse, insulting remarks, taunting scorn, or social omission by his/her colleagues, subordinates, and supervisors. Johnson and Gardner (2001) stated that workplace bullying happens regardless of employees' race, religion, nationality, gender, color as well as creed. Moreover, several terminologies have been used for this deviant behavior such as; bullying in the place of work, deviance in the place of work, incivility, violence in the work environment as well as aggression in the working atmosphere, etc. Additionally, bullying in the work environment causes different mental illnesses in the employees such as demoralization, depression, anxiety as well as frustration. Cooper, Hoel, Einarsen & Sheehan (2011) and Einarsen & Nielsen (2012) cited that bullying in the workplace negatively influences the attitudes and well-being of employees as well as incurs costs for companies and affects the performance of a company. Moreover, this deviant behavior of the workers in the place of work ruins the environment of a business as well as decreases the morale of workers by Einarsen, Hoel & Cooper (2003) and Jagatic & Keashly (2003).

Bullying in the workplace not only cause various consequences for the workers in companies but also impacts the performance of workers which is one of the most significant concerning area for the companies and human resource managers. Because companies maintain and determine the effectiveness and efficiency of a business through the performance of workers and bullying in the working place represents a substantial hazard for both employees and management, whose main objective is to verify that their companies work to amplify profit as well as secure the competitive edge in the market. Furthermore, this injustice behavior in the place of work (workplace bullying) leads to another deviant behavior called "counterproductive-work-behavior". The employees of a company perform this behavior against the unfair or injustice behavior in the place of work. Furthermore, Kelloway et al (2010) stated that this is a kind of behavior that shows the dissatisfaction of the employees in the organization. Additionally, according to Peterson (2002), the evolution of this deviant behavior of the workers is due to the discriminating behavior in the work environment. On average 24% of Australian workers become unproductive due to psychological stress caused by counterproductive work behavior to a Productivity Commission report (2010). In addition to this, there were an estimated 200 billion dollars in the aggregate financial loss every year in the USA Spector and Penney (2002) and 600 billion dollars in financial loss in the UK every year Ferris, et al (2009). Additionally, according to the Smithikrai study (2008), he stated that in Thailand 60% of workers become the victims of this counterproductive work behavior.

Additionally, CWB (counterproductive work behavior) is the volitional behavior of the worker that interrupts the important norms and operations of a business. According to Bennett and Robinson (1995), Spector et al (2006), and Sackett (2002), this deviant behavior of employees endangers the well-being of a business as well as its workers or both. Furthermore, some scholars estimate that the costs and the prevalence linked with counterproductive work behavior (CWB) differ greatly. They mainly approved that the

counterproductive work behavior (CWB) is damaging for the companies as well as for its staff. Additionally, Baron and Geddes (1997) described that approximately 69 percent of the executives and managers signaled to become victims of oral violence due to offering bad performance assessments. Besides this, the projected financial costs of counterproductive work behavior (CWB) are significant and lie between \$17.6 and \$200 billion by Langton and Hollinger (2006).

In the present market arrangement, a human asset has a huge influence on the competitive edge and sustainability of an organization. For that reason, the companies require to benefit the productivity of the employees (Noel & Hitlan, 2009). In contrast, negative attitudes in the environment of a company usually impress the perceptions of the employees which normally results in counter-productivity. Hence, this study attempts to determine the relationship between workplace bullying and counterproductive behavior and how workplace bullying leads to the dark behavior of employees.

Though there are few studies done before, analyzing the impact of workplace bullying (WB) on counterproductive work behavior (CWB). However, there were a few gaps that are described below:

- Prior studies have not considered the geographical context of Pakistan. There is only one such study in the same field conducted in Bangladesh (Sadia, 2017). Hence, it leads to a gap in the geographical context.
- Additionally, past studies considered only a small sample size targeting the respondents of either private banks or Logistics companies leaving behind other sector employees (Peng, 2016; Meltem&Mubeyyen, 2020 Sadia, 2017). This leads to selection bias due to the lower sample size. Additionally, there is a gap in analytic methodology as past studies only considered Regression Analysis.

This study will help the organizations improve their policies, adopt sound management practices as well as develop a good work environment that encourages organizational efficiency through employee wellbeing and performance as well as constructing a productive work company as stated by Murphy and Sauter Lim (1996).

2. Review of Relevant Literature

2.1. Workplace Bullying

WB (workplace bullying) is categorized as one of the deviant behaviors of the workers in the organizations. Skogstad&Einarsen (1996) and Rayner, (1998) stated that generally one of the ten employees becomes a victim of bullying. Rayner (1995) reported that those individuals who were victims of bullying or who observed bullying quit their positions due to bad or negative experiences. Furthermore, Lewis (1999) stated that in such a situation the sufferers determine it hard to protect themselves as opposed to the behaviors of other individuals. The bullying conducts contains hard-hitting eye interaction, menacing physical movements as well as attempts to erupt. In a study by Keashly, (1998), the intimidating behavior, as well as the publicizing of misleading speculations about the sufferer, is also involved in bullying.

According to Einarsen (1999), he stated that the substantial, intentional, or unintentionally repeated actions of bullying toward one or more employees cause a sense of distress, and embarrassment as well as decreased the performance of employees in the work climate between the sufferers. According to Baron & Neuman (1996), very few studies have been performed on minor types of maltreatment including impolite comments, reckless acts, or destructive gestures. However, a survey was conducted by Baron & Neuman (1996) which showed that several times aggression occurs in the work environment is less severe such as verbal but not physical, passive compared to active, indirect instead of direct as well as subtle instead of overt.

Nielsen and his coworkers (2010) stated that globally 15 percent of workers faced these negative attitudes which are known as bullying. Likewise, according to the report of Nielsen and Einarsen (2015), 11 percent of the population becomes bullying victims. According to Stallworth and Fox (2005) state that workplace bullying is experienced by people working in the companies a minimum of once in the last 5 years. Lutgen Sandvik & his colleagues (2007) state that. 47 percent of USA workers experienced WB (workplace bullying) in the previous 2 years. Lastly according to Boddy (2014) that there is a strong and positive correlation between WB (workplace bullying) as well as CWBs (counterproductive work behaviors).

Moreover, Romano (1994), stated that more than 20% of the HR executives contributed to the research that experienced violence in the workplace in their companies in the 1990s. While 33% reported fears of violence in the work environment. Likewise, according to the report of North-Western National Life Insurance Company (1993), throughout a year, approximately 2.2 million employees experienced physical assaults, 6.3 million employees were terrorized as well as 16.1 million employees were bullied. According to the survey conducted by Bjorkqvist, Osterman, and Hjelt-Back (1994) from three hundred and thirty-eight university workers in Finland, determined that 32% of employees experienced verbal harassing conduct in the workplace.

In this current situation, WB (workplace bullying) is big trouble for businesses. Bullying entails a place where one or more individuals sense themselves exposed to deviant behavior from other individuals over an extended period. The impact of WB (workplace bullying) on the organization and employees also convey this idea to the light. Furthermore, the development of the corporation's grievances about intimidation also shows a key role in examining negative attitudes in the workplace including bullying as well as mobbing. Likewise, Einarsen et al (2011) reported that eliminating somebody in the social climate or persuading a colleague's job sustainability with aberrant emotions and harassment is classified as workplace bullying. According to the notion of Kaplan (1975), workplace bullying is the organization's particular norms. While according to the research of Bennett & Robinson (1995), WB (workplace bullying) is the behavior that willingly disobeys the norms of an organization which not only threatens the staff members but also the business itself.

According to Johnson & Gardner (2001), bullying in the work environment is a regular as well as annoying mental harassment including humiliation and condemnation. Namie (2003) reported that bullying in the work environment is a frequent, ill-behaved, health-threatening abusive treatment of an employee. Research by Einarsen et al (1994)

states that harassment and bullying in the workplace is a significant dilemma. According to the research of Crawford & Adams (2009), the executives or leaders who have authority and power, they might usually use the tactics of bullying their other employees to obtain their personal benefits. These behaviors by top management or executives due to more authoritative power and they determine it easy-going to misuse their authority and power in support of organizational effectiveness. So, it proves that the leaders or executives are favoring these negative behaviors. According to the report of Brodsky (1976), bullying in the work environment needs at least compliance by supervision. An issue of bullying might take various shapes including excessive workload, bullying, work disruption, retaliation, etc. According to Ferris (2004), the victims of bullying typically do not receive any fair-minded support from their senior executives or leaders when they complain about bullying in the work environment. According to Ferris (2004), it may be possible that the representatives to take the side of the bully and dismiss or warn the worker who complained.

2.2. Counterproductive Work Behavior

The negative attitudes of the workers in the management and organizations get higher every day. Thus, the CWB (counterproductive work behavior) is considered the most used notion for negative and deviant attitudes in the place of work by Heyde et al (2014). According to them, CWB (counterproductive work behavior) is a behavior of an employee with an intention to harm the business, staff, clients, managers, leaders, and investors. CWB is classified as a sensible behavior that has a devastating risk on the company and its employees by Fox and Spector (2005). According to Treviño et al (2006) & Sulea et al. (2015), counterproductive work behaviors (CWBs) are the behaviors of the individuals displayed in the correct situations which are injurious to the business or persons. Hence, the work conditions including the business culture are very essential variables of counterproductive work behaviors (CWBs).

Various researches have been done on counterproductive work behavior (CWB) and every researcher used distinct terms to suggest this corresponding set of destructive actions. (Neuman & Baron (1997) Spector (1978) used the term “aggression” for CWB, (Hollinger, 1986; Bennett & Robinson (1995) used the term “deviance”, Folger & Skarlicki (1997) used the term “retaliation”, and Kramer, Bies & Tripp (1997) used the terminology of “revenge” for CWB (counterproductive work behavior). Generally, CWB involves the misuse and destruction of business property, performing work or job incorrectly, or neglecting to inform the superiors regarding errors and work issues such as a mechanical failure as well as withdrawal (includes taking sick leave when he/she is not sick).

Additionally, CWB (counterproductive work behavior) has a marvelous negative influence on productivity loss, increased the insurance expenses, damaged the property of a company, and amplified the turnover rate Neuman & Baron (1996) and Benminson, (1994) Kelloway & LeBlanc (2002) and Vigoda (2002), and amplified dissatisfaction in individuals by MacLean, Keashly & Trott (1994) as well as experienced the work stress. The counterproductive work behavior (CWB) can be better understood through the work stress model by Spector (1998), who states that the ecological stressors are observed by persons in the form of experiencing the negative feelings (including anxiety or anger) which might result in responses to stressors, known as work strains.

Beehr&Jex (1991) categorized the work strains into physical, behavioral, or psychological strains. The behavioral strains including yelling at the co-employee, staying at home instead of working in the workplace as well as reducing the quantity or quality of work are also considered as part of counterproductive work behavior (CWB). The behavioral strain is an alternative for people to manage the stressor by decreasing the feelings provoked by the stressor (including alcohol drinking or escaping from work) or by reducing the stressor himself (such as discussing with the manager and creating a solution).

3. Hypotheses Development

Rahim Kozako and Safin (2013), the perception of the individual about the attributions and environment for the occasions, emotive responses, and capabilities are commonly associated with personality traits. Leymann (1996) and Pervin (1993) reported the significance of personality and character on the emotions, feelings, behaviors, and attitudes of human beings.

Colbert and his coworkers (2004) focused on the variances of the employees' personality traits which can affect the work climate. In the Attitude Behavior Theory of Fishbein and Ajzen (1977), the personality of the employee and CWB (counterproductive work behavior) are linked to one another. Furthermore, the dissimilarities in the personality of the employee make the variation in counterproductive work behaviors (CWBs) Rahim, Kozako and Safin (2013), Bowling et al (2011), Spector (2005), Elliot (2010), Trevino, KishGephart and Harrison (2010), O'Neill and Hastings (2009). On the other hand, the negative behavior of the workers' perception of the place of work events also initiates the counterproductive work behaviors in the companies to Douglas, Martinko, and Gundlach (2002).

Bowling and his associates (2011) examined the research about CWBs and found that the forecasters of these attitudes were eminent as situational forecasters including work-stressor, leadership styles as well as personality traits including neurotics and conscientiousness. According to the research of Rahim, Kozako, and Safin (2013), they found a negative association between the CWB and conscientiousness. Furthermore, Scott, Ones, and Berry (2007) examined the association between counterproductive work behaviors (CWBs) and personality traits and found that agreeableness is associated with CWBI and conscientiousness is related to CWBO. Additional research outcomes also showed that conscientiousness and agreeableness are adversely linked with CWBs by Mullins-Sweatt, Deshong, and Gront (2015).

Similarly, Persson and colleagues (2016) indicated that emphasizing the variations of people might be useful for knowing the bullying issues. Einarsen, Matthiesen& Nielsen (2008) also described that the personality traits of a sufferer perform a vital role in bullying behaviors. For instance, several elements like low emotive stability, neuroticism, and low point conscientiousness are constructively associated with bullying behaviors by Glaso et al (2007). Commonly, the bullying victims work tougher to intercede the aggressive stress of the bully. Knardahl& Nielsen (2015) observed that the victimization of WB (workplace bullying) is associated with decreased degrees of conscientiousness. Additionally, Glaso et al (2007), Desoto, Hitlan&Cliffon (2006), and Bacharach & Bamberger (2006) state that

the association between conscientiousness and bullying is negative. Additionally, conscientiousness boosts the productivity of workers as well as competition in a company that might result in a bias toward other workers. Furthermore, if the expectations of employees related to bonuses, promotions, or rewards do not fulfil or if the employees are not appreciating their work and efforts, then they might also recognize it as bullying behavior on them Knardahl & Nielsen (2015).

Referring to the above explanations, this study was intended to determine the relation between WB (workplace bullying) and CWBs (counterproductive workplace behaviors). The research model and hypothesis were formulated in accordance with the literature. The research model is formulated in which WB (workplace bullying) is an independent variable and CWB (counterproductive work behavior) is a dependent variable in this diagram.

The following hypothesis has been formulated.

H₁: Workplace bullying has a significant positive impact on counter productive work behavior.

4. Research Methodology

The main objective of the study was to analyze the impact of workplace bullying on counterproductive work behavior hence quantitative research design was followed. In other words, the conclusive research design opted for the study as the study is interested in finding the descriptive statistics of the participants and the causal relationship between workplace bullying and counterproductive work behavior (CWB). The population of this study was the overall employees working in the banking sector of Mardan. Using convenient sampling techniques was used to collect the data from the participants of the study. The technique was adopted based on the availability of the participants. Hence, the data was collected from 125 participants from 22 banks.

In order to address the above objectives, primary data with the help of a closed-ended multifactor questionnaire was developed. The questionnaire was placed on a 5 Point Likert Scale (PLS). For each dimension such as workplace bullying, and counterproductive work behavior different constructs were developed.

Using SPSS 20, initially, descriptive statistics of the participants were figured out. Apparently, to analyze the impact of workplace bullying on counterproductive work behavior initially correlation analysis and regression analysis were performed.

5. Findings & Discussion

The main objective of the study was to investigate the impact of workplace bullying on counterproductive work behavior. For this purpose, initially, the self-developed multifactor questionnaire reliability was tested, and thereafter descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and multiple linear regression analysis were performed. As shown below:

5.1. Reliability Test

To aim the study's objective, the instrument designed for the study has been tested using the measure of Cronbach alpha. Initially, the value of Cronbach alpha was estimated for shame acknowledgment, shame displacement, and counterproductive work behavior. From the estimates, it has been observed that each factor's reliability is appropriate such as Shame Acknowledgement ($\alpha = 0.813$), shame displacement ($\alpha = 0.648$), and counterproductive work behavior ($\alpha = 0.893$). Finally, the overall instrument's reliability was tested. From the estimates, it has been observed that the reliability of the overall instrument is appropriate as the value of Cronbach alpha was 0.845. As shown in the table. 1. below:

Table 1. Reliability Test

Variables	Factors	Items	Value of Cronbach Alpha
Workplace Bullying	Shame Acknowledgement	6	0.813
	Shame Displacement	4	0.648
CWB		10	0.893
Overall		20	0.845

Source: Author's Own Analysis Using SPSS V20

5.2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

From a total of 125 bank employees, the responses have been recorded. While considering the demographics, gender, age, highest qualification, job status, and current ranks have been considered. Each is described stepwise, as below:

Table 2. below describes the gender of the study respondents. It has been observed that the majority (50.4%) of the respondents who participated were female followed by the second highest (49.6%) number of female respondents. It has been observed that the majority (31.2%) of the respondents were in the age bracket between 25 and 35 years followed by the second-highest number of respondents (33%) in the age bracket between 36 and 45 years. Additionally, the least number of respondents were in the age bracket between 55 and older years. In addition, it has been observed that the majority (31.2%) of the respondents were holding a Master's degree followed by a bachelor's (24%). Finally, it has been observed that the majority (82.4%) of the respondents who took participation in the study were

permanently followed by the second-highest number of respondents who were contractual employees (17.6%).

Table 2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Description	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	62	49.6	49.6
	Female	63	50.4	100
Age	25-35	39	31.2	31.2
	36-45	33	26.4	57.6
	46-55	29	23.2	80.8
	55 and over	24	19.2	100
Education Level	Bachelors	30	24	24
	Masters	39	31.2	55.2
	MS	28	22.4	77.6
	PhD.	28	22.4	100
Nature of Employment	Permanent	103	82.4	82.4
	Contract	22	17.6	100

N = 125

5.3. Correlation Analysis

After estimating the demographic profile of the respondents, correlation analysis was performed to check the correlation between the variables of interest such as shame acknowledgement (SA), shame displacement (SD) and counter productive work behavior (CWB). From the below estimates it can be observed that there is a strong positive correlation (0.853) between shame acknowledgement (SA) and counter productive work behavior (CWB) though there is a weak positive correlation (0.414) between shame displacement (SD) and counter productive work behavior (CWB). As shown in table 3. below.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis

Variables	CWB	SA	SD
CWB	1	.414**	.853**
Shame Displacement	.414**	1	.303**
Shame Acknowledgement	.853**	.303**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

5.4. Regression Analysis

The table 4. Below illustrates the model summary of the regression analysis. The value of R squared shows the percentage of variation explained by predictor variables for the dependent variable. From the value of R squared of 0.754, it can be stated that a total of 75.4% of the variation in dependent variable is explained by workplace bullying (shame acknowledgement and shame displacement).

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.868a	.754	.750		.74192

a. Predictors: (Constant), Shame Acknowledgement, Shame Displacement

The table 5. Below illustrates the analysis of variance of the regression analysis. ANOVA basically describes the overall model significance. From the sig. value of 0.00 it can be stated that the overall model is significant or in other words, the results of the overall model is valid and is appropriate.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	205.773	2	102.887	186.913	.000b
	Residual	67.155	122	.550		
	Total	272.928	124			

a. Dependent Variable: CWB

b. Predictors: (Constant), Shame Acknowledgement, Shame Displacement

The table 6. Below illustrates the table of coefficients. From the table of coefficients, it can be observed that both the subfactors of workplace bullying namely shame acknowledgment and shame displacement have significant impact on counterproductive work behavior (CWB). Shame acknowledgements have a strong positive significant (beta = 0.623) impact on the counter productive work behavior while shame displacement have a weak positive significant (.160) impact on counterproductive work behavior (CWB).

Table 6. Table of Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.692	.163		4.248	.000
	Shame Displacement	.160	.044	.172	3.645	.000
	Shame Acknowledgement	.623	.037	.801	16.993	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CWB

6. Conclusion

WB (Workplace bullying) is measured as a major problem in organizations that have numerous adverse outcomes for both organization and workers. This concept of WB (workplace bullying) was introduced by Leymann in 1996. He also explained the behaviors which entail a place where 1 or more individuals sense themselves exposed to deviant behavior from other individuals over a prolonged period. Some of the bullying conducts are ignorance, withholding info, impractical targets, demeaning remarks, coercion, verbal

threats, or criticism by Ayoko, Callan, and Härtel (2003). Additionally, O'Moore and his coworkers (1998) determined that WB (workplace bullying) not only affects psychological and physiological health (such as sleep illnesses, high rates of anxiety, trouble in concentration, lower self-efficiency and self-esteem, depression, burn-out, mental health difficulties) of workers but also impact victim's career. Spector and Bruk-Lee (2006) state that the workers who experience adverse feelings or unhappiness will react with CWBs against the individuals triggering these adverse feelings. According to Boddy (2014), the firm psychopaths have a significant effect on bullying as well as these individuals also perform a key role in the existence of CWB (counterproductive work behavior).

Moreover, it is understood that the problems of employees directly influence the productivity of an organization. One of the main problems in sustaining the effectiveness and efficiency of the organizations is employee performance and WB (workplace bullying) becomes a noticeable hazard for the organizations whose major objective is to certify the employees' performance at the peak level to amplify profit as well as a secure competitive edge in the market by Devonish, (2013). Moreover, WB (workplace bullying) rises cynicism by Tekin, Kaya & Tekpınar (2019), organizational silence by Demirtas, Knoll & Harlos (2018), anti-productive firm behaviors by Einarsen et al (2011), intention to resign by Ma, Wang & Hsieh (2019), decreased job engagement by Einarsen et al (2018) as well as lesser OC (organizational citizenship) by Galan, Domingez & Constantino (2006).

While on the other side, CWBs (counterproductive work behaviors) had been defined as a protest inside the company by participants to show their disappointment or behaviors to solve the injustice by Kelloway et al (2010). For instance, destroying the supplies and material of a firm, performing somebody's job inaccurately as well as harming a precious property of a business are considered as CWBs (counterproductive work behaviors) by Härtel, Callan & Ayoko (2003).

Furthermore, the experimental results indicated that WB is a behavior that is damaging to a company. Thus, companies should place their main significance on stopping the WB (workplace bullying). The organizations must establish a pleasant job environment and creates an anti-bullying action in the company's culture. So that the organizations resolutely entranced in every employee's mind. The managers and supervisors should be cautious towards the emotive enervation which has a direct link with CWBs and the bullying. Each business should establish a bias-free job environment for their employees where employees can work easily and freely. This research is helpful for companies and executives to understand WB (workplace bullying) and its effect on CWB (counterproductive workplace behavior). The executives then can make sure that this sort of unwelcomed conduct would not take place in the company. The company could also keep a check on employers and supervisors to stop the mental and physical harm of the sufferer and give emotional support to them.

6.1. Recommendations & Implications

The implications of this study might aware managers of the impact of workplace bullying on the performance of employees which can be either indirect or direct. It also recommends to directors and executives the requirement of appreciating and value the well-being of their workers which is an essential performance predictor. Furthermore, this study helps the HR practitioners and policymakers to develop an effective risk-controlling system

through which they can enhance the mental well-being and job satisfaction of workers such as training, rehabilitation, and counseling programs as well as decrease the CWBs and bad performances of employees. Moreover, workplace health management professionals can also deliver frequent educational sessions on job-linked stressors (including bullying as well as other social factors) for the advantage of managers and employees because education is an impetus for the change and development in an organization.

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